

Structural Investigations of 1-Amidino-2-thiourea Complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II)

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The infrared spectra of metal complexes of 1-amidino-2-thiourea (HATU) with Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) have been measured in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} and some observed bands have been assigned. The assignments of bands have been checked by examining the spectra of deuterated ligand and its Ni(II) complex. The reflectance spectrum of solid Ni(ATU)_2 shows a broad peak at 22.73 kK and shoulder at 17.24 kK which are attributed to d-d transitions. The spectrum of $[\text{Cu(ATU)}](\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{SO}_4$ has two shoulders at 19.23 kK and 17.24 kK, which are most probably due to d-d transition bands. The X-ray powder patterns of Ni(ATU)_2 are different from those of Pd(ATU)_2 indicating that these two complexes are not isostructural.

The preparation and properties of the complexes of 1-amidino-2-thiourea (HATU),

with Co(II and III), Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II), Hg(II) and Pt(II) have been reported by Rây *et al.*^{1,2,3}. However, their structures are not known. In the present work the structures of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes of HATU have been investigated by infrared, reflectance and X-ray diffraction methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

The metal complexes were synthesized by following the procedure described by Ray *et al.* The nickel complex was found to be identical with the compound, Ni(ATU)_2 , prepared by them. Although they prepared the palladium complex as a hydrated compound of composition $\text{Pd(ATU)}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by drying the complex in air, the same could only be prepared in the anhydrous form by drying the product over P_2O_5 under vacuum. The anhydrous compound, Pd(ATU)_2 , is insoluble in water and most of the common organic solvents. The copper complex prepared by drying it over P_2O_5 under vacuum was found to have the composition $[\text{Cu(ATU)}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{SO}_4$, though the air dried compound was reported¹ to have the formula $[\text{Cu(ATU)}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. However, the properties of the copper compound prepared in the present investigation were found to be identical with those of the compound prepared by Rây *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The results of analysis of these compounds are given in Table I.

1. P. Rây and S. N. Chaudhury, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**, 673.
2. S. N. Poddar and P. Rây, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 279.
3. P. Rây, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 313.

TABLE I

Chemical Analyses of Metal Complexes of 1-Amidino-2-thiourea

Compound		%Metal	%N	%S
Ni(ATU) ₂	Found	20.73	38.00	21.56
	Required for Ni(C ₂ H ₅ N ₄ S) ₂	20.05	38.26	21.86
	Required for Ni(C ₂ H ₅ N ₄ S) ₂ · 1.5H ₂ O	18.35	35.07	20.01
[Cu(ATU)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ SO ₄	Found	24.47	21.38	18.52
	Required for [Cu(C ₂ H ₅ N ₄ S)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ SO ₄	24.01	21.16	18.14
	Required for [Cu(C ₂ H ₅ N ₄ S)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ SO ₄ · 4H ₂ O	21.13	18.63	15.97
Pd(ATU) ₂	Found	30.91	32.94	18.65
	Required for Pd(C ₂ H ₅ N ₄ S) ₂	31.23	32.91	18.82
	Required for Pd(C ₂ H ₅ N ₄ S) ₂ · 3H ₂ O	27.09	28.35	16.20

Reflectance and Absorption Spectra : A Hilger and Watts ultra-violet Spectrophotometer was employed to measure the absorption spectrum of ATU in methanol (E. Merck's extra pure). The reflectance spectra of solid complexes were taken on a UNICAM spectrophotometer, Model SP 500, with standard MgCO₃ block supplied with the instrument. The samples were powdered to particle size of about 15 μ in a mechanical grinder and no diluent was used.

Infrared spectra were measured on a Perkin-Elmer Infrared recording Spectrophotometer, Model 21, with NaCl and KBr prisms. The samples were prepared in KBr pellets and the spectra were verified by taking measurements in nujol mull. The results were checked by examining the spectra of deuterated HATU and Ni(ATU)₂.

Deuterated HATU was prepared by repeated recrystallization of the reagent from deuterium oxide of purity better than 99.4%. The deuterated Ni(ATU)₂ was obtained by adding solution of nickel salt in D₂O to a solution of deuterated reagent in D₂O.

X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the complexes were taken with 19 cm UNICAM Camera using Cu K- α radiation. The intensity of the lines were measured visually.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ultra-violet spectrum (Fig. 1) of 1-amidino-2-thiourea in methanol solution shows three strong absorption peaks at 46.95 kK ($\epsilon = 9233 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 41.67 kK ($\epsilon = 14,990 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 36.76 kK ($\epsilon = 11,230 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The position and intensity of these peaks suggest that they are probably due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. Comparison of the spectra of the HATU with the spectra of its S-ethyl derivative *viz.*, N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea hydrobromide,⁴ (HN = C—NH—C—NH₂ · HBr) shows that the peak at 36.76 kK is not

present in the spectra of the S-ethyl derivative. It is reported that^{5,6} that the compounds

4. A. Paigankar and B. C. Haldar, Proc. XI International Conference on Coordination Chemistry, Haifa, September 1968.
5. K. S. Suresh, J. Ramachandran and C. N. R. Rao, *J. Sci. Industr. Res. (India)*, 1961, 20B.
6. A. Dutta Ahmed and P. K. Mandal, *J. Inorg. and Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2347.

containing thicarbonyl group usually show a strong absorption band near 36.76 kK and so, it appears quite plausible that this band is associated with the thiocarbonyl group.

Fig. 1 : Absorption Spectrum of 1-amidino-2-thiourea in Methanol. Conc.:— $9.304 \times 10^{-5} M$.

The reflectance spectrum (Fig. 2) of solid $Ni(ATU)_2$ shows a very broad peak at 22.73 kK and a shoulder at around 17.24 kK which may be assigned to d-d transition bands. A square planar diamagnetic nickel(II) complex of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea, $Ni(ASETU)_2$ also shows a broad band at 25.0 kK and a shoulder at 21.28 kK.⁴ Thus, it seems reasonable

Fig. 2 : Reflectance Spectra of Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes of 1-amidino-2-thiourea.

that diamagnetic $Ni(ATU)_2$ may also have square planar configuration. The spectrum of the copper complex (Fig. 2) shows two shoulders at 17.24 kK and 19.23 kK which are most probably due to d-d transitions.

The infrared spectra of HATU (Fig. 3 and 5) show a number of strong and weak bands in the region $3430-3090 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which appear at the expected lower frequencies in the spectra

Fig. 3 : Infrared Absorption Spectra of 1-amidino-2-thiourea and Deuterated 1-amidino-2-thiourea in Nujol.

Fig. 4 : Infrared Absorption Spectra of Ni(ATU)₂ and Deuterated Ni(ATU)₂ in Nujol.

of the deuterated compound. These bands are assigned to NH stretching vibrations, being in the region reported for NH stretching band in the literature⁷. The hydrogen bonding may be responsible for the occurrence of stretching frequency of NH₂ at a frequency lower than that of free NH₂. The bands in the region 3400–3240 cm⁻¹ are also observed in the spectra of Ni(ATU)₂, Pd(ATU)₂ and [Cu(ATU)(H₂O)₂]₂SO₄ (Figs. 4–7). As expected, the spectra of the deuterated Ni(ATU)₂ reveal bands at the corresponding lower frequencies. The free NH₂ group might be present in the metal complexes but there is no firm evidence to prove it. The copper complex does not show any absorption band above 3300 cm⁻¹. The broad and strong band at 3300 cm⁻¹ in this complex may be due to overlapping of the stretching frequency of coordinated water molecule with that of NH stretching. This complex also

Fig. 5: Infrared Absorption Spectra in KBr Pellets.

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|-------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| 1. HATU | 2. Deuterated HATU. |
| 3. Ni(ATU) ₂ | 4. Deuterated Ni(ATU) ₂ . |

7. K. Nakanishi, *Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy—Practical*, Holder Day Inc., San Francisco and Nankodo Ltd., Tokyo, 1962, p. 40.

exhibits two weak and broad peaks at 2390 and 2200 cm^{-1} which are not observed in HATU, Ni(ATU)_2 and Pd(ATU)_2 . These peaks are also missing in the spectra of HASETU.HBr, Ni(ASETU)_2 and Co(ASETU)_2 .⁴ It may be noted that the palladium complex of N-amidino-

Fig. 6 : Infrared Absorption Spectra of Cu(II) and Pd(II) Complexes of 1-amidino-2-thiourea in Nujol.

S-ethyl-thiourea, which contains water molecules, has an absorption peak of medium intensity at 2230 cm^{-1} .⁸ Further, it may be pointed out that a very weak and broad band near 2340 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of nickel dimethylglyoxime, sodium and potassium hydrogen dimethylglyoxime have been assigned to the OH—stretching by Blinc and Hadzi⁹. It is therefore, quite possible that the peaks at 2390 cm^{-1} and 2200 cm^{-1} in the copper complex of HATU arise due to H_2O . Some of the important infrared frequencies and their assignments are tabulated in Table II.

HATU and its Ni(II) complex show two bands near 1640 cm^{-1} and 1615 cm^{-1} . The band at 1640 cm^{-1} is shifted to 1210–1218 cm^{-1} on deuteration and so it has been assigned to bending vibration of NH_2 . 1615 cm^{-1} band does not shift on deuteration. It may be due to unperturbed $\text{C}=\text{N}$. In copper(II) complex it appears at 1610 cm^{-1} . Copper(II) complex also shows a new band at 1665 cm^{-1} which may be due to bending of coordinated water.

8. A. Paigankar, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1968, p. 128.

9. R. Blinc and D. Hadzi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4536.

TABLE II

Some of the Important Infrared Bands of ATU, and its Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II) Complexes and their Assignments

1-Amidino-2-thiourea		Ni(ATU) ₂		[Cu(ATU) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ SO ₄	Pd(ATU) ₂	Assignment
Undeuterated cm ⁻¹	Deuterated cm ⁻¹	Undeuterated cm ⁻¹	Deuterated cm ⁻¹	cm ⁻¹	cm ⁻¹	
3420(St,Sp)	2580(M,Sp)	3440(St,B)	2580(St,Sp)	—	3420(Sh)	} ν NH
3300(St,B)	2430(W,B)	3320(M,Sp)	2420(M,Sp)	—	3390(St,Sp)	
3090(St,B)	2510(M,Sp)	3240(M,Sp)	2390(M,Sp)	3300(St,B)	3300(St,B)	
—	—	—	—	2390(W,B)	—	} ν H ₂ O
—	—	—	—	2200(W,B)	—	
—	—	—	—	1665(St,B)	—	δ H ₂ O
1645(Sh)	1218(M,Sp)	1640(St,Sp)	1210(St,Sp)	—	1645(Sh)	δ NH ₂
1615(St,Sp)	1620(W,B)	1610-15(M,B)	1620(St,Sp)	1600-10(St,B)	1610(St,Sp)	ν C = N
1515(St,B)	1505(M,Sp)	1510(M,B)	1505(S,Wp)	1515(St,Sp)	1510(Sh)	N—C = S(1)
1320(M,Sp)	1320(M,Sp)	1340(M,Sp)	1345(M,Sp)	1340(M,B)	1320(St,Sp)	N—C = S(2)
935(M,Sp)	935(M,Sp)	930(St,Sp)	930(St,Sp)	965(M,Sp)	965(M,Sp)	N—C = S(3)
740(M,Sp)	735(M,Sp)	740(M,Sp)	735(Sh)	720(M,Sp)	715(W,Sp)	ν C = S
—	—	605(M,Sp)	710(M,Sp)	600(Sy,Sp)	562(M,Sp)	} M-N Vibra- tions.
—	—	509(M,Sp)	505(M,B)	490(M,Sp)	440(M,Sp)	

St = Strong, Sp = Sharp, B = Broad, M = Medium, Sh = Shoulder, W = Weak.

There has been great indefiniteness with regard to the assignment of the C=S stretching frequency in nitrogen containing compounds. The assignment in these compounds varies in the wide range of 850–1570 cm⁻¹. The observed bands are due to mixed vibration of C–N stretching, C = S stretching, and NH₂ rocking. Rao and Venkataraghavan¹⁰ have divided the relevant compounds into two classes on this basis. They pointed out that, where nitrogen atoms are attached to the thiocarbonyl group, there seem to be three regions in which a C = S vibration, coupled with other vibrations, may be observed. This appears to be a useful concept, although of the three arbitrary regions viz., 1570–1395 cm⁻¹, 1420–1260 cm⁻¹ and 1140–940 cm⁻¹, the lowest should be extended to 700 cm⁻¹ to include absorptions which have recently been shown to exhibit contribution from C = S stretching vibration.^{11–14} The spectra of HATU show three bands at 1510, 1320 and 935 cm⁻¹ which are not shifted on dueteration. They are also not observed in HASETU.HBr and its metal

10. C. N. R. Rao and R. Venkataraghavan, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1962, **17**, 541.

11. K. Swaminathan and H. M. N. H. Irving, *J. Inorg. and Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1291.

12. M. Mashima, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1964, **37**, 974.

13. A. Yamaguchi, R. B. Penland, S. Mizushima, T. J. Lane, C. Curran and J. V. Quagliano, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 527.

14. K. A. Jensen and P. H. Nielser, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1966, **20**, 597.

complexes which contains $-\text{S.C}_2\text{H}_5$ group in place of thiocarbonyl group⁴. The bands at 1510, and 1320 cm^{-1} in HATU appear more or less at the same place in the spectra of its Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes. These bands mostly come from deformation vibrations of NH_2 and stretching vibration of C-N. However, the band at 935 cm^{-1} in HATU may have an appreciable contribution of C = S stretching. This band occurs at 930 cm^{-1} in Ni(ATU)₂, while it is appreciably shifted in Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes (965 cm^{-1}), possibly indicating the presence of M-S linkage in these two complexes. The band at 740 cm^{-1} in the ligand, which may be due to mixed vibration with some contribution from N-C = S bending vibration, is observed at 720 cm^{-1} and 715 cm^{-1} in Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes respectively, but it appears at the same position (740 cm^{-1}) in Ni(II) complex. Recently Wiles *et al.*¹⁵⁻¹⁶ have reported that thiosemicarbazones show a band in the region 840-815 cm^{-1} which they have assigned to C = S stretching coupled with N-C-N. They believe that this band may shift by 100 cm^{-1} depending upon the nature of the compound.

Fig. 7 : Infrared Absorption Spectra of Cu(II) and Pd(II) Complexes of 1-amidino-2-thiourea in KBr Pellets.

15. D. M. Wiles, B. A. Gingras and T. Suprunchuk, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 469.

16. D. M. Wiles and T. Suprunchuk, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 2258.

The ligand HATU has no absorption band in the region $617\text{--}470\text{ cm}^{-1}$, whereas Ni(ATU)₂ shows two new bands at 600 cm^{-1} and 507 cm^{-1} which are not significantly shifted on deuteration. The M–N vibrations in the chelated Co(II and III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes usually appear in the region $400\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$.^{17–19} Further, the band at 526 cm^{-1} in Ni(ASETU)₂ has been attributed to Ni–N stretching vibrations⁴. It is quite reasonable to assume that the bands at 600 cm^{-1} and 507 cm^{-1} in Ni(ATU)₂ are also due to Ni–N vibrations. These bands probably appear at 600 cm^{-1} and 490 cm^{-1} in Cu(II) complex and at 562 cm^{-1} and 440.5 cm^{-1} in Pd(ATU)₂.

The X-ray powder patterns of Ni(ATU)₂ (Fig. 8) are different from those of Pd(ATU)₂ suggesting that these two complexes are not isostructural.

The results of present investigation can be explained on the basis of the following structures proposed by Ray *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). However, other structures are also possible.

17. K. Nakamura, *J. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1959, **80**, 1348.
18. K. Ueno and A. E. Martell, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 998; *ibid.*, 1956, **60**, 1270.
19. N. J. Patel and B. C. Haldar, *J. Inorg. and Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1037.

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